

An Investigation Into How First Class Children Model Multi-digit Addition and Subtraction Problems

Sinéad McGill

St. Joseph's National School

This paper reports on an investigation into how first class children model multi-digit addition and subtraction problems. This case study was carried out within a Delivering Equality of Opportunity In Schools Band One school. The children were presented with problems and thematic lessons were designed using the addition and subtraction problem-structures outlined by Van de Walle et al. (2020). The data was analysed according to the Ongoing Assessment Project Additive Framework (Hulbert & Ebby, 2017). This study demonstrates that first class children can use models such as manipulative materials, prepared images and the empty number line to determine successful solutions to word problems.

Keywords: mathematical modeling, addition, subtraction

Introduction

This paper focuses on how first class children model multi-digit addition and subtraction problems. This research was carried out in the author's classroom within a Delivery Equality of Opportunity in Schools (DEIS) Band One school. In this paper, the strategies and models the children used are explored and analysed.

Literature Review

Over the last number of decades, mathematical modeling has become more prominent in mathematics education literature (Blum, 2015) and has also come to the forefront of mathematical curriculum development in Ireland (National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA), 2022). Mathematical modeling is seen to bridge informal understanding with more abstract formal mathematical ideas (Kaiser et al., 2011). Therefore, it would seem fitting that the development of mathematical modeling would be one of the more significant goals of mathematics education (English & Sriraman, 2010). Using a variety of models offers multiple levels of learning (Suh & Seshaiyer, 2016). Consequently, the inclusion of mathematical modeling could enable all children to develop mathematical concepts at their own level.

Models

Engaging with models can provide children with the opportunity to model mathematical ideas and leads to unstructured problem solving (Suh & Seshaiyer, 2016). Manipulative materials and the Empty Number Line (ENL) are discussed below.

Manipulative Materials. Research emphasises that the use of manipulative materials aid children to make sense of mathematics at their own level. Their incorporation is not a new idea in mathematics education and holds many benefits, including helping students to focus on mathematical ideas and stimulating higher order thinking (Clements & McMillen, 1996). However, "busy hands don't necessarily mean busy minds" (Waite-Stupiansky & Stupiansky, 1998, p. 85). Therefore, it is imperative for students' mathematical development that when

using manipulative materials, there is a conversation between the student and teacher which links concrete materials and abstract ideas (MacLellan, 1997).

ENL. The ENL is a model that can support “children in using a variety of sequential calculation strategies” (Murphy, 2011, p. 148). It is an internationally acknowledged model for developing mental mathematic strategies (Bramald, 2000) and was developed as many children were experiencing problems with two-digit arithmetic (Bobis & Bobis, 2005). It was originally created by the Dutch and was encompassed in their Realistic Mathematics Education (Murphy, 2011). Much of their improved performance in international standardised testing has been directly associated with its introduction (Bramald, 2000).

Methodology

Van de Walle et al. (2020) outlined three ways in which word problems can be structured; change (join and separate), part-part-whole and compare. Within each of these categories there are three subcategories, each naming a different way the question can be structured or framed (Van de Walle et al., 2020). These are outlined in detail in Table 1. When designing the research tasks, each category and subcategory was used to ensure that the children were exposed to every type of word problem. Each lesson focused on a different problem type, apart from lesson three, which revised the children’s learning from lessons one and two. This research explores and documents first class children’s use of models to record their strategies when solving multi-digit addition and subtraction problems. A cohort of fifteen children participated in six mathematics lessons. Their solutions were discussed with their peers and were recorded using the tools provided. These included cubes, lollipop sticks, prepared images, pencils and paper. Discussions of strategies took place after they had reached their own solutions and the teacher researcher then recorded their strategy using an ENL. As the lessons progressed, the children also had the opportunity to share their strategy with their peers, however, the use of the ENL was optional for them. Samples and photographs of the children’s work, teacher observations and audio recordings of one group of children were used to collect the data during lessons.

Table 1

Problem type and structure (Van de Walle et al., 2020, p. 187)

Type	Result Unknown	Change Unknown	Start Unknown
Change- Join	Sandra had 8 pennies. George gave her 4 more. How many pennies does Sandra have altogether? $8+4=\square$	Sandra had 8 pennies. George gave her some more. Now Sandra has 12 pennies. How many did George give her? $8+\square=12$	Sandra had some pennies. George gave her 4 more. Now Sandra has 12 pennies. How many pennies did Sandra have to begin with? $\square+4=12$

Change-Separate	Sandra had 12 pennies. She gave 4 more pennies to George. How many pennies does Sandra have now?	Sandra had 12 pennies. She gave some to George. Now she has 8 pennies. How many did she give to George?	Sandra had some pennies. She gave 4 to George. Now Sandra has 8 pennies left. How many pennies did Sandra have to begin with?
	$12-4=\square$	$12-\square=8$	$\square-4=8$
	Whole Unknown	One Part Unknown	Both Parts Unknown
<i>Part-part-whole</i>	George has 4 pennies and 8 nickels. How many coins does he have?	George has 12 coins. 8 of his coins are pennies and the rest are nickels. How many nickels does George have?	George has 12 coins. Some are pennies and some are nickels. How many of each coin could he have?
	$4+8=\square$	$12=4+\square$ or $12-4=\square$	$12=\square+\square$
	Difference Unknown	Larger Quantity Unknown	Smaller Quantity Unknown
<i>Compare (situation of more)</i>	George has 12 pennies, and Sandra has 8 pennies. How many more pennies does George have than Sandra?	George has 4 more pennies than Sandra. Sandra has 8 pennies. How many pennies does George have?	George has 4 more pennies than Sandra. George has 12 pennies. How many pennies does Sandra have?
	$8+\square=12$	$8+4=\square$	$\square+4=12$
<i>Compare (situation of fewer)</i>	George has 12 pennies. Sandra has 8 pennies. How many fewer pennies does Sandra have than George?	Sandra has 4 fewer pennies than George. Sandra has 8 pennies. How many pennies does George have?	Sandra has 4 fewer pennies than George. George has 12 pennies. How many pennies does Sandra have?
	$12-8=\square$	$\square-4=8$	$12-4=\square$

Findings and discussion

The findings offer an insight into the models used to solve addition and subtraction problems. The On Going Assessment Project (OGAP) Additive Framework (Hulbert & Ebby, 2017) was used to analyse the strategies employed. Strategies were sorted into three categories: counting (ones), transitional (tens) and additive. The progression begins with

counting (ones), which is the most basic level and extends to the additive category, which is the most complex and efficient level. This section analyses the strategies used.

Counting (Ones) Strategies

Direct Counting. Direct counting was utilised in various ways, from using the resources to drawing images. Concrete materials were used regularly to model addition and subtraction problems in lessons one and two. It accounted for 67% of the strategies employed by two of the three groups in the first two lessons. This result could suggest that these children initially needed concrete materials to build meaning of the new mathematical structures (Clements, 1999). The concrete materials assisted them towards an answer as they “moved, grouped and re-arranged” to illustrate a problem (Putri et al., 2020, p. 83).

Figure 1.

Examples of direct counting strategies employed by first class children.

The above figure 1(i) highlights how the problem was modeled using concrete materials. Initially looking at Figure 1(i), the method by which the children solved this problem is not evident. It was noted in the field notes that in order to reach this solution, the children initially counted the full set of thirty-one lollipop sticks and then split them into two sub-sets, the stickers that Mohammed had and the ones Megan gave him. These actions replicated the problem structure of change unknown and suggests a good understanding. It could also suggest that the concrete materials were enabling the children to understand the part-part-whole relationship of numbers. Figure 1(ii) highlights another way in which direct counting was applied. Despite this solution looking unlike the previously presented solution, they are quite similar. The child drew images to replicate the problem presented, and although they were not using physical concrete materials, they created their own visual equivalent. Rellensmann et al. (2016) suggests that the drawing of images is a good starting point for conceptual understanding. This research seems to echo this, as all word problems were correctly solved by the children drawing images and they applied more complex additive and transitional strategies as the research progressed.

Counting With Prepared Images. The children utilised prepared images to count sets and solve the given problems. Giving the children images could be viewed as one way to

aid children towards an adequate visual representation of the word problem, which many children have difficulties with (Boonen et al., 2011). 60% of the pairs of children used these images at least once over the course of the six lessons to solve a given word problem and for the most part were successful in finding its solution. Although this strategy falls into the most basic level of early counting strategies within the counting (ones) level of the OGAP Additive Framework (Hulbert & Ebby, 2017), its use was not without reason. As suggested in the framework, “as students learn new concepts or interact with new problem situations and problems structures, they may move up and down along this progression” (Hulbert & Ebby, 2017, p. 2). Given that five of the six lessons introduced new problem types and structures, it is not surprising that this strategy was the most prominent used by two table groups.

Counting in Ones With ENL. Using the OGAP Additive Framework (Hulbert & Ebby, 2017), this strategy is seen as one that exists within the second tier of the more basic counting strategies, counting (ones). However, this framework fails to note the transition from using concrete materials to an abstract tool such as the ENL. This transition reveals that the children understand the problem and can represent this in an abstract form (Putri et al., 2020).

Counting On. The counting on strategy was achieved for the most part through the use of concrete materials. Similar to the direct counting strategy, some children drew images and counted on from them. This is more complex than direct counting and more efficient, however it still falls into the counting (ones) category (Hulbert & Ebby, 2017). Hulbert and Ebby (2017) do note that it falls into the top tier of counting (ones) category, suggesting that it is a stepping stone to early transitional strategies. Mc Intosh (2006) considers this counting on or back in ones problematic, as it is inefficient but this fails to realise that this was a development for some children, away from direct counting. However, there is some merit in Mc Intosh’s (2006) recommendations stating that teachers should encourage children who are secure in this method to move onto mental mathematics strategies. Counting on with the standard number line was an unforeseen strategy and was heavily influenced by the classroom environment. It was not until discussing strategies that it was realised its use to problem solve. Some children jumped back or forward in ones on the standard number line, which would classify as counting on with a visual model, counting (ones) strategy (Hulbert & Ebby, 2017). This strategy was particularly favoured by one group in lesson six. Before utilising this strategy, the children in this group relied solely on direct counting strategies using images or concrete materials. This is the lower level of the counting (ones) strategy (Hulbert & Ebby, 2017). However, this framework does not account for the fact that using the standard number line prompts direct counting (Clements, 1999). This is the case as children merely located a number on the number line and counted on the number being added. In order to utilise mental counting strategies, children would need to keep track of the number they are counting and how many they are adding (Clements, 1999).

Transitional (Tens) Strategies

Inefficient Use of ENL. The ENL was used inefficiently when solving three of the eighteen problems. Despite this, this strategy did not necessarily portray a lack of

understanding of mathematical concepts. The data shows that some of the children did in fact understand the problems, but tried to create a unique solution to share it with their peers.

Efficient Use of the ENL. The efficient use of the ENL is “jumps by multiples of ten on a number line” and “jumps by a ten and efficient groups of ones” (Hulbert & Ebby, 2017, p.2). This strategy was applied by the one group in every lesson, with multiple solutions on the ENL becoming more prominent in later lessons. This research highlighted that the ENL can be used as a flexible tool by first class children in which they can represent their thinking. Van den Heuvel-Panhuizen (2008) found that for some children the ENL could be seen as constraining, however, it depended on the way in which it was taught. Within this research, this model was not taught explicitly and the children were introduced to it as a means of modeling and sharing ideas, which was not the case in Van den Heuvel-Panhuizen’s (2008) research. Confining the children to an ENL could limit children’s thinking as they could focus on using this abstract tool and not fully engage in understanding the mathematical problem.

Figure 2.

Examples of transitional (tens) strategies utilised by first class.

Figure 2(i) above demonstrates an efficient use of a model by jumping in “10s and efficient groups of ones” (Hulbert & Ebby, 2017, p.2). This was only one of the solutions produced on the ENL, which promoted flexibility and use of mental strategies in the research lessons.

Additive Strategies

Using 10s. Bridging ten is when “part of the second number is used to make the first number up to the next multiple of 10, and then the remainder of the second number is added” (Chesney, 2013, p.38). This strategy is one of the more complex on the OGAP Additive Framework, falling into the additive category. In this research using 10s usually went alongside the use of the ENL as a model. This is possibly a result of the children’s strategies being modeled in the share sessions on the ENL. This was a favourite strategy employed by one group of children, equating to 20% of their strategies used. Figure 2(ii) outlines how one child modeled his 10s strategy using the ENL. This problem prompted the children to subtract, and this is visible from the subtracting sign on the first jump.

Fact Recall and Derived Facts. Fact recall is when a child remembers a number fact without having to work it out. In this study, doubles (i.e. adding the same number to itself)

were recalled when solving two different problems. Recalling number facts from memory leads to a very efficient problem-solving strategy (Leutzinger, 1999). When utilizing the strategy of derived number facts, known number facts are utilised to derive another. This is one of the more complex strategies utilised in these lessons and some of the children worked systematically, using previous number facts to work out another. Using this additive strategy portrays a deep level of understanding. It is interesting how this strategy was first employed by the children in lesson three, as this lesson was a revision lesson and contained problem structures already seen by the children. Using the strategy of derived facts recognises that the children are “developing more sophisticated ideas about number, recognizing ways to think about basic fact combinations” (Van de Walle et al., 2020, p. 184).

Flexible Compensation. Interestingly, this strategy was only seen in the first problem of the first lesson. After the introduction of the ENL, this strategy never made a reappearance. Perhaps, this demonstrates one of the weaknesses of the ENL, that flexible compensation is a strategy which is very difficult to record on the ENL. This was highlighted in the field notes; it was difficult to demonstrate the compensation strategy used in problem one on the ENL. It was noted that some of the children found it difficult to follow this strategy on the ENL until they questioned the children that used it. Possibly, this reasoning alone deterred some from using it throughout the lesson series, as they found it challenging to record it on the ENL.

Conclusion

This research has highlighted the potential of mathematics modeling in junior class within a DEIS context. This is particularly valid within the Irish primary education context, with the new Primary Mathematics Curriculum incorporating a high degree of mathematical modeling (NCCA, 2022). During this research, first class children used a range of models such as manipulative materials, prepared images and the ENL to determine successful answers to word problems. It confirmed that first class children can model multi-digit addition and subtraction problems.

References

- Blum, W. (2015). Quality teaching of mathematical modelling: what do we know, what can we do? In S. J. Cho (Ed.), *The proceedings of the 12th international congress on mathematical education: intellectual and attitudinal challenges* (pp. 73–96). Springer.
- Bobis, J., & Bobis, E. (2005). The empty number line: Making children’s thinking visible. In M. Coupland, J. Anderson, & T. Spencer (Eds.), *Making mathematics vital: Proceedings of the 20th biennial conference of the Australian Association of Mathematics Teachers* (pp.66-72). AAMT.
- Boonen, A. J. H., Van Wesel, F., Jolles, J., & Van der Schoot, M. (2011). The role of visual representation type, spatial ability, and reading comprehension in word problem solving: An item-level analysis in elementary school children. *International Journal of Education Research*, 68, 15-26.
- Bramald, R. (2000). Introducing the empty number line. *Education 3-13*, 28(3), 5-12.

- Chesney, M. (2013). Mental computation strategies for addition: There's more than one way to skin a cat. *Australian Primary Mathematics Classroom*, 18(1), 36-40.
- Clements, D. H. & McMillen, S. (1996). Rethinking 'concrete' manipulatives. *Teaching Children Mathematics*, 2(5), 270-279.
- Clements, D.H. (1999). 'Concrete' manipulative, concrete ideas. *Contemporary Issues in Early Childhood*, 1(1), 45-60.
- English, L., & Sriraman, B. (2010). Problem solving for the 21st century. In L. English & B. Sriraman (Eds.), *Theories of mathematics education: seeking new frontiers* (pp. 263-290). Springer Berlin-Heidelberg.
- Hulbert, E. T., & Ebby, C. B. (2017). *OGAP Additive Framework*. The Ongoing Assessment Project. http://www.ogapmath.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/framework_November2017.pdf
- Kaiser, G., Blum, W., Ferri, R. B., & Stillman, G. (2011). *Trends in teaching and learning of mathematical modelling*. Springer.
- Leutzing, L. P. (1999). Developing thinking strategies for addition facts. *Teaching Children Mathematics*, 6 (1), 14-18.
- Maclellan, E. (1997). The role of concrete materials in constructing mathematical meaning. *Education 3 to 13*, 25(3), 31-35. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03004279785200311>
- Mc Intosh, A. (2006). *Mental computation of school-aged students: Assessment, performance levels and common errors*. CiteSeerX. <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.523.134&rep=rep1&type=pdf>
- Murphy, C. (2011). Comparing the use of the empty number line in England and in the Netherlands. *British Educational Research Journal*, 37(1), 147-161. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01411920903447423>
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA) (2022). *Primary mathematics curriculum draft specification for consultation*. https://ncca.ie/media/5370/draft_primary_mathematics_curriculum_specification.pdf
- Putri, H. E., Muqodas, I., Wahyudy, M. A., & Nuraeni, F. (2020). The effect of Concrete-Pictorial-Abstract (CPA) Approach on the decrease of mathematical anxiety in primary school. *International Conference on Elementary Education*, 2(1), 80-93. <http://proceedings.upi.edu/index.php/icee/article/view/609>
- Rellensmann, J., Schukajlow, S., & Leopold, C. (2016). Make a drawing- effects of strategic knowledge, drawing accuracy, and type of drawing on students' mathematical modelling performance. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 95, 53-78. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10649-016-9736-1>
- Suh, J., & Seshaiyer, P. (2016). *Modeling mathematical ideas: developing strategic competence in elementary and middle School*. Rowman & Littlefield.
- Van de Walle, J.A., Karp, K. S., & Bay-Williams. J.M. (2020). *Elementary and middle School mathematics: teaching developmentally* (Global ed.). Pearson Education.